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**ENHANCEMENT OF HYDROCARBON DEGRADATION OF CRUDE OIL
CONTAMINATED SOIL THROUGH ORGANIC AMENDMENT**

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ABSTRACT

*Crude oil contamination threatens soil health, plant growth, and microbial diversity, particularly in oil-producing regions. This study evaluated the potential of sawdust, an abundant lignocellulosic waste, to enhance hydrocarbon degradation in crude oil-contaminated soil. Three treatments were established: uncontaminated control soil, crude oil-contaminated soil without amendment, and crude oil-contaminated soil amended with sawdust. Physicochemical analyses revealed that crude oil pollution caused soil compaction and strong hydrocarbon odor, while sawdust amendment improved soil texture, aeration, and reduced odor intensity over time. Maize (*Zea mays*) growth served as a bioindicator of soil recovery. In untreated contaminated soil, no seed germination or shoot development occurred. By contrast, sawdust-treated samples showed significant growth, with shoot lengths averaging 13.2 ± 0.7 cm and enhanced leaf and stem development by day fourteen, indicating restored soil fertility. Microbial counts on nutrient agar and potato dextrose agar revealed higher fungal proliferation in sawdust-amended soils. Identified fungal*

isolates included Aspergillus, Rhizopus, Mucor, and Penicillium spp., supporting enhanced bioremediation. These findings confirm that sawdust functions as an effective biostimulant, promoting microbial activity, increasing biodiversity, and accelerating hydrocarbon breakdown. This study highlights sawdust as a low-cost, eco-friendly remediation strategy for restoring crude oil-contaminated soils, especially in developing regions.

KEYWORDS: Enhancement, Hydrocarbon, Degradation, Crude oil, Contaminated, Soil, Organic, Amendment

INTRODUCTION

Soil pollution from crude oil is a major environmental problem, especially in oil-producing areas. Petroleum operations like drilling, exploration, storage, transport, processing, and refining often cause hydrocarbon spills, resulting in terrestrial oil pollution that typically contains hydrophobic compounds (Chettri et al., 2021). As indicated by Al-Hawash et al., (2019), Crude oil pollution impairs biodiversity, pushing out sensitive plants and cutting down soil microbial variety. Hydrocarbon breakdown in contaminated soils usually happens slowly because they don't dissolve well and aren't easily available to microbes.

Conventional cleanup methods often lack effectiveness or harm the environment. Recent research has looked into bioremediation, using organic materials like sawdust to boost microbial breakdown of hydrocarbons. Al-Hawash et al. (2019) showed that mixing NPK fertilizer with sawdust greatly improved crude oil biodegradation in contaminated soils, proving the potential of organic amendments for remediation.

Sawdust, a residue from wood processing, has been studied as a potential soil amendment for phytoremediation. It can also be repurposed as a carbon source for wastewater treatment, making it valuable for environmental cleanup and sustainable waste management (Kayode et al., 2022). Research shows that repurposing organic waste materials such as sawdust contributes to environmentally friendly waste management, helping to reduce pollution and promote a cleaner, more sustainable environment (Kayode et al., 2022).

Dashti et al. (2020) examined biochar, a substance comparable to sawdust, as a support for bacteria that degrade petroleum and reported encouraging outcomes in hydrocarbon breakdown, but thorough research specifically on sawdust is still limited, emphasizing the need for more studies on its advantages and drawbacks. Also, Umeojiakor et al. (2019) used pumpkin leaves and sawdust to supply nutrients that boost indigenous microbes, enhancing the biodegradation of crude oil-contaminated soil in Nigeria's Niger Delta.

Oil spills from crude and refined petroleum in aquatic environments cause serious environmental damage, leading to the loss of marine life and harming economies, especially in regions involved in oil production and transport (Onuorah et al., 2020).

This study therefore aims to evaluate the enhancement of hydrocarbon degradation of crude oil contaminated soil through organic amendment using sawdust.

METHODOLOGY

- **Research Design**

This study employed a laboratory-based experimental design to assess sawdust's effectiveness as an organic amendment for enhancing hydrocarbon degradation in crude oil-contaminated soil. Clean soil samples were artificially contaminated with a known amount of crude oil and then treated with different concentrations of sawdust. The setup included control groups (untreated contaminated soil) and experimental groups (sawdust-treated) under controlled laboratory conditions. Hydrocarbon degradation was tracked over time using standard analytical methods. As Adlane et al. (2020) noted, experimental designs are especially useful in controlled remediation studies because they isolate treatment effects and enable replication and statistical analysis. Similarly, they highlighted the importance of structured laboratory trials for optimizing bioremediation strategies in petroleum-contaminated environments.

- **Sample Collection and Preparation**

Soil samples were obtained from a clean, uncontaminated site, then air-dried, sieved, and homogenized to achieve uniform particle size. Crude oil was thoroughly mixed into the prepared soil. Sawdust was then incorporated into the contaminated soil at different proportions. The mixtures were placed in plastic containers and incubated at room temperature for a set period, with moisture levels maintained by regular watering.

- **Application of Saw Dust Amendment**

Sawdust from untreated wood was air-dried, sieved, and thoroughly mixed into the contaminated soil in respective containers and maintained under laboratory conditions (room temperature, moderate moisture) with regular turning for aeration, while the experiment included three sample types: a control of uncontaminated soil with no crude oil or sawdust, soil contaminated with crude oil but no bioremediation agent, and soil contaminated with crude oil and treated with sawdust as a bioremediation agent (Rong et al., 2021).

- **Measurement of Maize Plants**

The effectiveness of the amendments was measured by monitoring and recording the weekly growth of shoots, leaves, and stems from plants grown in soil amended with sawdust compared to the control.

- **Fungal Identification and Characterization**

The sub-cultured fungi were identified by their cultural and morphological features, including mycelia, spore type, and fruiting bodies, using a lactophenol cotton blue wet mount examined under a compound microscope at 40x magnification, with observed structures compared to a fungal atlas for identification (Catherine et al., 2015).

RESULTS

Findings from this study are presented in tables as indicated below;

Table 1: Measurement of Plant Growth and Observation (Maize)

Samples	Days	Shot	Leaves	Stem
Control (Uncontaminated soil)	Day0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Day7	5.1±0.4	2±1	1.2±0.1
	Day14	9.2±0.6	5±1	1.8±0.2
Soil + Crude Oil (No Sawdust)	Day0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Day7	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Day14	0.0	0.0	0.0
Soil + Crude oil + Sawdust	Day0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Day7	6.5±0.5	3±1	1.5±0.1
	Day14	13.2±0.7	13.2±0.7	2.1±0.2

Table 2: Fungal Populations

Treatment Group	Day1	Day3	Day5
Control	4.5×10 ²	5.5×10 ²	6.0×10 ²
Crude Oil Only	4.5×10 ²	4.0×10 ²	4.5×10 ²
Crude Oil + Sawdust	3.8×10 ²	6.0×10 ²	6.5×10 ²

Table 3: Fungal Isolates

Fungal Genus	Hyphal Type	Spore Type	Optimal Temp (°C)	Optimal pH	Notable Features
<i>Aspergillus</i>	Septate hyphae	Conidia	25–37	3.0–7.0	Filamentous, dominant in degradation
<i>Rhizopus</i>	Aseptate hyphae	Sporangiospores	25–30	4.5–6.5	Common in organic matter decomposition
<i>Mucor</i>	Aseptate hyphae	Sporangiospores	20–30	4.0–7.0	Grows fast, involved in biotransformation
<i>Penicillium</i>	Septate hyphae	Conidia	20–30	4.0–6.5	Contributes to biodegradation

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows Maize seeds failed to germinate in the crude oil-contaminated soil without any treatment, clearly showing the phytotoxic effects of hydrocarbons on plant development. In contrast, the sawdust-amended soil supported noticeable seed germination and plant growth, though the growth rate and vigor were slightly lower than those observed in the uncontaminated control group. This suggests that while sawdust can help reduce hydrocarbon toxicity and promote plant establishment, it may not completely eliminate stress on seedlings. This is in agreement Nnamdi and Suripino (2020) demonstrated the effectiveness of composting crude oil-contaminated soil using sawdust as a bulking agent, achieving an impressive 93% degradation of total petroleum hydrocarbons after a 22-week period. This highlights the potential of organic amendments like sawdust not only to support plant growth but also to enhance microbial breakdown of petroleum contaminants in soil. In addition, a study by Greg (1999) on plant species thriving in petroleum-contaminated environments aligns with and reinforces the current study’s findings, suggesting that certain plants can tolerate and even aid in remediation of hydrocarbon-polluted soils.

Table 2 shows the steady increase in fungal populations in the amended samples indicating that sawdust helps boost fungal survival and supports their degradation activity. The highest fungal growth was recorded in the setup containing both crude oil and sawdust, suggesting that sawdust not only provides a supportive environment for fungi but also enhances their ability to thrive in hydrocarbon-contaminated soils. This highlights the potential of sawdust as an effective amendment for stimulating fungal communities involved in bioremediation. This is in agreement with the research of Obemeata et al. (2022) who observed a comparable trend, noting that bacterial counts rose significantly from four weeks after remediation when spent engine oil-polluted soil was biostimulated with sawdust and cow blood. Together, these studies reinforce the idea that organic amendments like sawdust create favorable conditions for microbial proliferation, enhancing biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons. Similarly, findings align with Rita et al. (2023), who reported increases in both initial and final populations of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Aspergillus flavus* when sawdust was used as a soil amendment, highlighting its role in supporting microbial growth.

Table 3 shows the fungal isolates identified from the soil sample, which included *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, *Mucor*, and *Penicillium*. The presence of these fungi likely contributed to the effectiveness of the sawdust amendment, helping to support and enhance the growth of maize plants in the contaminated soil. These fungal species are known for their tolerance to hydrocarbon stress and their ability to produce enzymes that break down complex organic pollutants, which may have reduced the toxicity of the crude oil and created a more favorable environment for plant root development. Their activity possibly improved soil structure and nutrient cycling, further promoting maize seedling establishment and vigor in the amended treatments. Rita et al. (2023) reported the presence of *Aspergillus flavus* in soil contaminated with spent engine oil, highlighting their potential role in hydrocarbon degradation. Their findings suggest that these microorganisms can tolerate and even thrive in oil-polluted environments, making them promising candidates for bioremediation efforts. This supports the idea that certain bacteria and fungi naturally adapt to petroleum contamination and can contribute to reducing its toxic effects on soil health. Aneke and Okafor (2025) isolated similar fungal isolates such as *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger* from crude oil-polluted soil, suggesting their tolerance to hydrocarbon contamination and potential role in bioremediation.

CONCLUSION

Sawdust proved effective in improving soil properties, enhancing microbial proliferation, and supporting plant growth in crude oil-contaminated soil. The increased microbial diversity in sawdust-amended soil, particularly the presence of fungi and other hydrocarbon-degrading microbes, highlights its potential for stimulating broad-spectrum hydrocarbon degradation. This makes sawdust a promising, low-cost, and eco-friendly solution for field-scale remediation of petroleum-contaminated environments.

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